

SURFACE TREATMENT EFFECTS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIBER REINFORCED POLYCARBONATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was discussed about the effects of surface treatments on mechanical properties of glass fiber reinforced polycarbonate injection moldings. Polycarbonate and fibers treated by an aminosilane coupling agent and a urethane binder were compounded and specimens were injection-molded. Tensile test, fatigue test and instrumented impact test were conducted, and the fiber length were also measured. Tensile strength were influenced by the treatment due to improvement of both the fiber length and the adhesion at the resin/fiber interface. It indicated that the binder had no adhesion but increased the fiber length resulting in strength improvement. Knee points appeared at the S-N curve and the effect of surface treatment disappeared in the long life range. The impact strength was influenced by the fiber length less than for the static tensile and fatigue strengths.

INTRODUCTION

Applications of glass fiber reinforced thermoplastics (FRTP) are expanding in the field of structural and mechanical parts because of the superior mechanical properties, the light weight, high productivity due to the injection molding process. The surface treatment of fibers is quite important for design of FRTP injection moldings as well as fiber dimensions, fiber content and fiber orientation. The effect of surface treatment for FRTP, however, have never been studied as much as glass mat reinforced thermosetting resin. A binder has little received much attention although it is used for any application.

In this study, the effects of surface treatments on the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced polycarbonate injection moldings are investigated. Particularly, the function of a urethane binder was aimed to elucidate during compounding and molding.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

Materials used in this study were polycarbonate (PC) produced by Mitsubishi Engineering Plastics Co., Ltd., Japan and E-glass fiber (GF) produced by Asahi Fiber Glass Co., Ltd., Japan. The diameter of fibers was 13 μm .

2. Surface treatment and compounding

An aminosilane coupling agent (APMS) and a urethane binder (UB) were used as surface treatment agents of GF. The treatment conditions were varied such that the concentration of both agents, APMS:UB were (A) 1:9, (B) 1:1, (C) 0:9 by weight. (Sample A was normal treatment condition, in Sample B amount of UB was lower than in Sample A and in Sample C APMS was not used.) Filaments were directly treated and bound by the agents and then were cut into 3 mm length. Treated GF and PC were compounded using a twin screw extruder KTX-30 made by Kobe Steel Works Co., Ltd., Japan. Fiber content was 20 wt%. PC was fed into the end of the cylinder through the main feeder and GF was fed into the middle of the cylinder using the screw-type side feeder after PC was completely molten. The compounding conditions were the same for Sample A, B and C. The cylinder temperature was 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the screw rotation was 300 rpm. Samples A1, A2, A3 were treated as same as Sample A but the compounding conditions were different. In the case of Sample A1 the cylinder temperature was 320 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the number of screw rotation was 300 rpm, and in the case of Sample A2 cylinder temperature was 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the number of screw rotation was 100 rpm, and in the case of Sample A3 the conditions of screw rotation was same as A1 but the cylinder temperature was reduced to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ after GF was fed (The temperature of the reservoir head was just set at 260 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The conditions of surface treatment and compounding condition are listed in *Table 1*.

Table 1 Surface treatment and compounding condition.

	Surface Treatment (by weight)		Compound Condition	
	APMS	UB	Number of Screw Rotation (rpm)	Set Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Sample A	1	9	280	300
Sample B	1	1	280	300
Sample C	0	9	280	300
Sample A1	1	9	280	320
Sample A2	1	9	100	280
Sample A3	1	9	280	260-300

3. Injection Molding

Compounded materials were fabricated into test specimens using an inline screw injection molding machine, N100BII, produced by Japan Steel Works Co., Ltd. The maximum clamping force was 980 kN and the maximum injection pressure was 170 MPa. All samples were molded under the same conditions in which the cylinder and mold temperature were 280 and 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively, and the screw speed was 50 mm/min and the holding pressure was 60 MPa. Dumbbell tensile specimens (ASTM standard type) with and without a weldline in the middle and flexure specimens were molded.

4. Measurement of fiber length

The residues in the extruder were picked from 7 sections of the screws after compounding. They were incinerated in an electric furnace at 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 h and the residual fibers were observed using a microscope and the average length by weight of 1000 fibers were measured.

5. Tensile test

Tensile test was conducted using INSTRON universal test machine 4206 at 5 mm/min of the crosshead speed and at room temperature and 50 %RH.

6. Fatigue test

Test specimens were cycled in an tensile apparatus mounted on an electrohydraulic fatigue test machine PAS-063 produced by Tokyo Koki Co., Ltd., Japan. The cyclic frequency was maintained at 10 Hz. Sine wave of tensile load with constant stress amplitude was supplied. No attempt was made to control the laboratory environment.

7. Impact test

For dynamic impact test, a Roland IFW instrumented impact testing machine was used. The test anvil was Charpy type and the span was 60 mm. Testing velocity was 1 m/s. The force supplied to the specimens was acquired and the data was smoothed with a 2 kHz filter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Fiber breakage in compound process

Figure 1 shows the variation of fiber length along the screw for Sample A, B and C. The length of fiber fed through the side feeder abruptly decreased from 3mm to 300-400 μm. During compounding the length decreased slowly, especially more slowly after kneading zone. Fiber were unbound in so short period that they were abruptly broken at the feeder zone. It was supposed that the fiber length could be controlled, if the time until fibers were sufficiently unbound could be controlled.

The ultimate fiber lengths at the die were 198, 157 and 212 μm for Sample A, B and C, respectively. The treatment conditions slightly influenced the fiber length.

Figure 1 Variation of average fiber length during compounding process in extruder, Fiber was fed at 400 mm of the screw position.

The effects of compounding conditions on the fiber length were remarkable. The fiber length of sample A1, A2 and A3 were longer than that of the above three samples. At the die area, the lengths of A1, A2, A3 were 342, 417, 278 microns, respectively. It was found that low screw rotation and high cylinder temperature were extremely effective to suppress the fiber breakage. It

was attributed to reduction of shear force during compounding process.

2. Effects on tensile strength

The results of tensile test were summarized in **Table 2**. The difference of strength between Samples A and B was caused by the difference of fiber length, and the difference between Sample A and C was by the adhesion between resin and fiber. It was noted that Weld strength was useful to estimate the bonding strength between fiber and resin because it was not influenced by fiber length in our previous study. Here Weld strength indicated Sample A and B had the same interfacial bonding strength but Sample C had a little lower one.

Table 2 Results of Tensile Test.

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	
	Non-weld	Weld
A	89.0	66.3
B	85.2	64.7
C	78.4	52.2
A1	90.4	
A2	88.7	
A3	91.8	

3. Effects on fatigue property

The S-N curves were illustrated in **Figure 2** for Sample A, B and C. In general, the curves were linear and the number of fatigue failure increased with the decrease of stress amplitude. In the range between 2 and 4.5 of logN, the curves of three samples were parallel. The fatigue strengths were corresponded with the tensile properties. Sample A which had the highest tensile strength indicated the longest life time. The curve of Sample A and B, however, had the bending point at about 4.5 of logN. In the long life range (logN>4.5), the slope of the curve increased sharply. Consequently, three curves converged on the same fatigue limit at 7 of log N. **Figure 3** indicated the S-N curves of Sample A1, A2 and A3. The same tendency was shown as in **Figure 2**. The slopes were same as Sample A in the short life range (logN<4.5), while they increased in the long life range (logN>4.5) resulting in almost the same fatigue limit. The critical knee points appeared at logN=4.5.

Figure 2 S-N Curves of Sample A, B and C.

Figure 3 S-N Curves of Sample A1, A2 and A3.

Figure 4 illustrated SEM photograph of the fracture surface of Sample A which was cycled with the lower stress. The thermal failure could be clearly observed around fibers. Circumference area with approx. 10 μm around fibers were fractured under thermal degradation by shear heat generated at the resin/fiber interface during cyclic test. It could not be observed in the specimen which was cycled with the higher stress. It was considered that, the heat generation was occurred significantly when the interfacial bonding strength was high. In such specimens, the crack initiated at the thermal failure around fibers. Therefore the knee point appeared and the lifetime decreased compared with the value predicted from the data in the short lifetime (dot line).

Figure 4 SEM Photo of Thermal Failure around Fiber in Fatigue Test (Sample A).

4. Effects on impact strength

Figure 5 illustrated the typical force-deflection curve measured by the instrumented impact test

machine for Sample A. The force was plotted as a function of time, and the deflection was proportional to the time. The impact force increased linearly with the time undulated. It was almost expended to the deformation of the specimens and the undulation was attributed to the crack initiation or propagation at the resin/fiber interface. The peak force was about 1.1 kN and the peak deflection was about 6 mm (at 6ms of time). The impact properties were measured of 5 pieces for each sample and the average value was calculated. The results were listed in **Table 3** for all samples.

Figure 5 Force-Deflection Curve in Instrumented Impact Test for Sample A.

Table 3 Results of Impact Test.

Sample	Peak Force (kN)	Peak Energy (J)	Peak Deflection (mm)
A	1.136	4.04	6.08
B	1.125	4.06	6.13
C	0.962	2.61	4.83
A1	1.127	3.94	5.76
A2	1.176	4.20	5.85
A3	1.163	4.23	6.12

The same impact properties could be recognized except Sample C. UB treatment without APMS provided low peak force, low peak energy and low peak deflections. There was no effects of the compounding conditions and UB concentration on the impact properties. The resin was found to remain around fibers in the fracture surface according to SEM observation, Thus the interfacial bonding strength was significantly high and the cracks proceeded though the resin phase around fibers not at the resin/fiber interface. In such case, the impact strength was improved by the ability of ductile resin to suppress the crack propagation.

CONCLUSIONS

This manuscript described the effects of surface treatments on the mechanical properties of glass fiber reinforced polycarbonate injection molding. Tensile strength were influenced by the treatment at the point of the fiber length and the adhesion at the resin/fiber interface. Weld strength indicated that the urethane binder had no adhesion. It, however, increased the fiber length resulting in improvement of Non-weld strength. The fatigue life time was well corresponded to the tensile strength. It was noted that a bending point appeared in the S-N curve and the effect of surface treatment decreased in the long life range or the low stress range. The impact strength was also similar but the fiber length influenced less than for tensile and fatigue strength.

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